

Appendix 3: A non-annotated checklist of Iranian spiders (i.e., 935 species, 324 genera, 55 families), excluding unpublished data, records of doubtful species previously rejected from the checklist of Iranian spiders, and those not identified to the species-level. The species that are known only from records in border areas are accompanied with a question mark. The order of listed families is based on their currently accepted evolutionary relationships. Within each family, species are listed alphabetically.

Mygalomorphae

Atypidae Thorell, 1870

***Atypus* Latreille, 1804**

1. *A. muralis* Bertkau, 1890
2. *A. piceus* (Sulzer, 1776)

Cyrtachenidae Simon, 1889

***Anemesia* Pocock, 1895**

3. *A. koponeni* Marusik, Zamani & Mirshamsi, 2014

Euagridae Raven, 1979

***Phyxioschema* Simon, 1889**

4. *P. gedrosia* Schwendinger & Zamani, 2018
5. *P. raddei* Simon, 1889

Nemesiidae Simon, 1889

***Raveniola* Zonstein, 1987**

6. *R. dunini* Zonstein, Kunt & Yağmur, 2018
7. *R. marusiki* Zonstein, Kunt & Yağmur, 2018
8. *R. mazandaranica* Marusik, Zamani & Mirshamsi, 2014
9. *R. niedermeyeri* (Brignoli, 1972)
10. *R. vonwicky* Zonstein, 2000

Theraphosidae Thorell, 1869

***Ischnocolus* Ausserer, 1871**

11. *I. jickelii* L. Koch, 1875
12. *I. vanandelae* Montemor, West & Zamani, 2020

Araneomorphae

Filistatidae Simon, 1864

***Filistata* Latreille, 1810**

13. *F. balouchi* Zamani & Marusik, 2020
14. *F. insidiatrix* (Forsskål, 1775)
15. *F. lehtineni* Marusik & Zonstein, 2014
16. *F. maguirei* Marusik & Zamani, 2015

***Microfilistata* Zonstein, 1990**

17. *M. magalhaesi* Zamani & Marusik, 2018

***Pritha* Lehtinen, 1967**

18. *P. garfieldi* Marusik & Zamani, 2015

***Sahastata* Benoit, 1968**

19. *S. amethystina* Marusik & Zamani, 2016
20. *S. sinuspersica* Marusik, Zamani & Mirshamsi, 2014

***Zaitunia* Lehtinen, 1967**

21. *Z. akhanii* Marusik & Zamani, 2015
22. *Z. alexandri* Brignoli, 1982
23. *Z. brignoliana* Zonstein & Marusik, 2016
24. *Z. darreshurii* Zamani & Marusik, 2018
25. *Z. medica* Brignoli, 1982
26. *Z. persica* Brignoli, 1982
27. *Z. vahabzadehi* Zamani & Marusik, 2016
28. *Z. zagrosica* Zamani & Marusik, 2018

Sicariidae Keyserling, 1880

***Loxosceles* Heineken & Lowe, 1832**

29. *L. coheni* Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2021

30. *L. persica* Ribera & Zamani, 2017

31. *L. rufescens* (Dufour, 1820)

32. *L. turanensis* Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2021

Scytodidae Blackwall, 1864

***Dictis* L. Koch, 1872**

33. *D. striatipes* L. Koch, 1872

***Scytodes* Latreille, 1804**

34. *S. arwa* Rheims, Brescovit & van Harten, 2006

35. *S. kumonga* Zamani & Marusik, 2020

36. *S. strandi* Spassky, 1941

37. *S. thoracica* (Latreille, 1802)

38. *S. univittata* Simon, 1882

Leptonetidae Simon, 1890

***Leptonetela* Kratochvíl, 1978**

39. *L. caucasica* Dunin, 1990 (?)

Pholcidae C.L. Koch, 1850

***Artema* Walckenaer, 1837**

40. *A. doriae* (Thorell, 1881)

41. *A. transcaspica* Spassky, 1934

***Crossopriza* Simon, 1893**

42. *C. khayyami* Huber, 2022

43. *C. parsa* Huber, 2022

44. *C. sengleti* Huber, 2022

***Nita* Huber & El-Hennawy, 2007**

45. *N. elsaff* Huber & El-Hennawy, 2007

***Pholcus* Walckenaer, 1805**

46. *P. alticeps* Spassky, 1932

47. *P. armeniacus* Senglet, 1974

48. *P. arsacius* Senglet, 2008

49. *P. caspius* Senglet, 2008

50. *P. elymaeus* Senglet, 2008

51. *P. hyrcanus* Senglet, 1974

52. *P. hystaspus* Senglet, 2008

53. *P. medicus* Senglet, 1974

54. *P. parthicus* Senglet, 2008

55. *P. persicus* Senglet, 1974

56. *P. phalangioides* (Fuesslin, 1775)

57. *P. velitchkovskyi* Kulczyński, 1913

***Physocyclus* Simon, 1893**

58. *P. globosus* (Taczanowski, 1874)

***Psilochorus* Simon, 1893**

59. *P. simoni* (Berland, 1911)

***Spermophora* Hentz, 1841**

60. *S. persica* Senglet, 2008

61. *S. senoculata* (Dugès, 1836)

62. *S. senoculatoides* Senglet, 2008

Caponiidae Simon, 1890

***Iraponia* Kranz-Baltensperger, Platnick & Dupérré, 2009**

63. *I. scutata* Kranz-Baltensperger, Platnick & Dupérré, 2009

Segestriidae Simon, 1893

***Segestria* Latreille, 1804**

64. *S. mirshamsii* Marusik & Omelko, 2014

65. *S. senoculata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Dysderidae C.L. Koch, 1837

***Dysdera* Latreille, 1804**

66. *D. achaemenes* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

67. *D. bakhtiari* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

68. *D. damavandica* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

69. *D. genoensis* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

70. *D. hormuzensis* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

71. *D. iranica* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

72. *D. isfahanica* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

73. *D. mazeruni* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

74. *D. medes* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

75. *D. persica* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023

76. *D. pococki* Dunin, 1985
 77. *D. sagartia* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023
 78. *D. tapuria* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023
 79. *D. verkana* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023
 80. *D. xerxesi* Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023
- Dysderella* Dunin, 1992**
 81. *D. transcaspica* (Dunin & Fet, 1985)
- Harpactea* Bristowe, 1939**
 82. *H. parthica* Brignoli, 1980
- Oonopidae Simon, 1890**
- Opopaea* Simon, 1892**
 83. *O. cornuta* Yin & Wang, 1984
 84. *O. sallami* Saaristo & van Harten, 2006
- Pelcinus* Simon, 1892**
 85. *P. amrishi* (Makhan & Ezzatpanah, 2011)
 86. *P. sengleti* Platnick, Dupérré, Ott, Baehr & Kranz-Baltensperger, 2012
- Triaeris* Simon, 1892**
 87. *T. stenaspis* Simon, 1892
- Trilacuna* Tong & Li, 2007**
 88. *T. qarzi* Malek Hosseini & Grismado, 2015
- Palpimanidae Thorell, 1870**
- Levymanus* Zonstein & Marusik, 2013**
 89. *L. dezfulensis* Zamani & Marusik, 2020
- Palpimanus* Dufour, 1820**
 90. *P. carmania* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
 91. *P. persicus* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
 92. *P. sogdianus* Charitonov, 1946
- Eresidae C.L. Koch, 1845**
- Eresus* Walckenaer, 1805**
 93. *E. adaleari* Zamani & Szűts, 2020
 94. *E. kollari* Rossi, 1846
95. *E. lavrosiae* Mcheidze, 1997
- Loureedia* Miller, Griswold, Scharff, Řezáč, Szűts & Marhabaie, 2012**
 96. *L. phoenixi* Zamani & Marusik, 2020
- Stegodyphus* Simon, 1873**
 97. *S. lineatus* (Latreille, 1817)
 98. *S. pacificus* Pocock, 1900
- Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862**
- Oecobius* Lucas, 1846**
 99. *O. cellariorum* (Dugès, 1836)
 100. *O. fahimii* Zamani & Marusik, 2018
 101. *O. ferdowsii* Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2017
 102. *O. ilamensis* Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2017
 103. *O. nadiae* (Spassky, 1936)
 104. *O. putus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876
- Uroctea* Dufour, 1820**
 105. *U. gambronica* Zamani & Bosselaers, 2020
 106. *U. grossa* Roewer, 1960
 107. *U. thaleri* Rheims, Santos & van Harten, 2007
- Hersiliidae Thorell, 1869**
- Bastanius* Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2016**
 108. *B. foordi* (Marusik & Fet, 2009)
 109. *B. kermanensis* Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2016
- Deltshevia* Marusik & Fet, 2009**
 110. *D. taftanensis* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
- Duninia* Marusik & Fet, 2009**
 111. *D. baehrae* Marusik & Fet, 2009
 112. *D. darvishi* Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2013
 113. *D. grodnitskyi* Zamani & Marusik, 2018
 114. *D. rheimsae* Marusik & Fet, 2009
- Hersilia* Audouin, 1826**

115. *H. talebii* Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2016
- Hersiliola* Thorell, 1870**
116. *H. artemisiae* Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2017
117. *H. macullulata* (Dufour, 1831)
118. *H. simoni* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
119. *H. sternbergi* Marusik & Fet, 2009
120. *H. turcica* Marusik, Kunt & Yağmur, 2010
- Uloboridae Thorell, 1869**
- Octonoba* Opell, 1979**
121. *O. yesoensis* (Saito, 1934)
- Uloborus* Latreille, 1806**
122. *U. plumipes* Lucas, 1846
123. *U. walckenaerius* Latreille, 1806
- Mimetidae Simon, 1881**
- Ero* C.L. Koch, 1836**
124. *E. aphana* (Walckenaer, 1802)
- Mimetus* Hentz, 1832**
125. *M. laevigatus* (Keyserling, 1863)
- Theridiidae Sundevall, 1833**
- Anelosimus* Simon, 1891**
126. *A. pulchellus* (Walckenaer, 1802)
127. *A. vittatus* (C.L. Koch, 1836)
- Asagena* Sundevall, 1833**
128. *A. phalerata* (Panzer, 1801)
- Crustulina* Menge, 1868**
129. *C. guttata* (Wider, 1834)
130. *C. sticta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1861)
- Dipoena* Thorell, 1869**
131. *D. melanogaster* (C.L. Koch, 1837)
- Enoplognatha* Pavesi, 1880**
132. *E. iraqi* Najim, Al-Hadlak & Seyyar, 2015
133. *E. latimana* Hippa & Oksala, 1982
134. *E. macrochelis* Levy & Amitai, 1981
135. *E. mediterranea* Levy & Amitai, 1981
136. *E. mordax* (Thorell, 1875)
137. *E. ovata* (Clerck, 1757)
138. *E. quadripunctata* Simon, 1885
139. *E. submargarita* Yaginuma & Zhu, 1992
140. *E. thoracica* (Hahn, 1833)
141. *E. turkestanica* Charitonov, 1946
- Episinus* Walckenaer, 1809**
142. *E. mikhailovi* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
143. *E. truncatus* Latreille, 1809
- Euryopsis* Menge, 1868**
144. *E. clara* Ponomarev, 2005
145. *E. mallah* Zakerzade, Moradmand & Jäger, 2022
146. *E. quinqueguttata* Thorell, 1875
147. *E. sexalbomaculata* (Lucas, 1846)
148. *E. schwendingeri* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
- Heterotheridion* Wunderlich, 2008**
149. *H. nigrovariegatum* (Simon, 1873)
- Kochiura* Archer, 1950**
150. *K. aulica* (C.L. Koch, 1838)
- Lasaeola* Simon, 1881**
151. *L. coracina* (C.L. Koch, 1837)
152. *L. prona* (Menge, 1868)
153. *L. tristis* (Hahn, 1833)
- Latrodectus* Walckenaer, 1805**
154. *L. cinctus* Blackwall, 1865
155. *L. dahli* Levi, 1959
156. *L. geometricus* C.L. Koch, 1841
157. *L. pallidus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872
158. *L. tredecimguttatus* (Rossi, 1790)
- Neottiura* Menge, 1868**
159. *N. bimaculata* (Linnaeus, 1767)
- Parasteatoda* Archer, 1946**
160. *P. lunata* (Clerck, 1757)
161. *P. tepidariorum* (C.L. Koch, 1841)
- Pholcomma* Thorell, 1869**
162. *P. gibbum* (Westring, 1851)
- Phoroncidia* Westwood, 1835**
163. *P. minuta* (Spassky, 1932)

Phycosoma O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1880

164. *P. inornatum* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1861)

Phylloneta Archer, 1950

165. *P. impressa* (L. Koch, 1881)

Platnickina Koçak & Kemal, 2008

166. *P. tinctoria* (Walckenaer, 1802)

Rhomphaea L. Koch, 1872

167. *R. sagana* (Dönitz & Strand, 1906)

Robertus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879

168. *R. arundineti* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871)

169. *R. lividus* (Blackwall, 1836)

Rugathodes Archer, 1950

170. *R. bellicosus* (Simon, 1873)

Simitidion Wunderlich, 1992

171. *S. simile* (C.L. Koch, 1836)

Steatoda Sundevall, 1833

172. *S. albomaculata* (De Geer, 1778)

173. *S. bipunctata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

174. *S. castanea* (Clerck, 1757)

175. *S. dahli* (Nosek, 1905)

176. *S. ephippiata* (Thorell, 1875)

177. *S. grossa* (C.L. Koch, 1838)

178. *S. maura* (Simon, 1909)

179. *S. nobilis* (Thorell, 1875)

180. *S. paykulliana* (Walckenaer, 1806)

181. *S. trianguloides* Levy, 1991

182. *S. triangulosa* (Walckenaer, 1802)

Theridion Walckenaer, 1805

183. *T. arsia* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

184. *T. cinereum* Thorell, 1875

185. *T. cyprusense* Wunderlich, 2011

186. *T. hemerobium* Simon, 1914

187. *T. hermonense* Levy, 1991

188. *T. hotanense* Zhu & Zhou, 1993

189. *T. innocuum* Thorell, 1875

190. *T. melanostictum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876

191. *T. melanurum* Hahn, 1831

192. *T. varians* Hahn, 1833

Mysmenidae Petrunkevitch, 1928

Microdipoena Banks, 1895

193. *M. jobi* (Kraus, 1967)

Tetragnathidae Menge, 1866

Meta C.L. Koch, 1836

194. *M. menardi* (Latreille, 1804)

Metellina Chamberlin & Ivie, 1941

195. *M. mendei* (Blackwall, 1869)

196. *M. merianae* (Scopoli, 1763)

197. *M. orientalis* (Spassky, 1932)

198. *M. segmentata* (Clerck, 1757)

Pachygnatha Sundevall, 1823

199. *P. clercki* Sundevall, 1823

200. *P. clerckoides* Wunderlich, 1985

201. *P. degeeri* Sundevall, 1830

Tetragnatha Latreille, 1804

202. *T. extensa* (Linnaeus, 1785)

203. *T. isidis* (Simon, 1880)

204. *T. montana* Simon, 1874

205. *T. nigrita* Lendl, 1886

206. *T. nitens* (Audouin, 1826)

207. *T. obtusa* C.L. Koch, 1837

208. *T. pinicola* L. Koch, 1870

209. *T. shoshone* Levi, 1981

Synsphyridae Wunderlich, 1986

Synsphyris Simon, 1894

210. *S. orientalis* Marusik & Lehtinen, 2003 (?)

Linyphiidae Blackwall, 1859

Agyneta Hull, 1911

211. *A. conigera* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1863)

212. *A. fuscipalpa* (C.L. Koch, 1836)

213. *A. iranica* Tanasevitch, 2011

214. *A. kopetdaghensis* Tanasevitch, 1989

215. *A. mesasiatica* Tanasevitch, 2000

216. *A. mollis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871)

217. *A. rurestris* (C.L. Koch, 1836)

Araeoncus Simon, 1884

218. *A. caucasicus* Tanasevitch, 1987

219. *A. humilis* (Blackwall, 1841)

220. *A. mitriformis* Tanasevitch, 2008
Archaraeoncus Tanasevitch, 1987
 221. *A. alticola* Tanasevitch, 2008
 222. *A. prospiciens* (Thorell, 1875)
Bathyphantes Menge, 1866
 223. *B. gracilis* (Blackwall, 1841)
Bolyphantes C.L. Koch, 1837
 224. *B. elburzensis* Tanasevitch, 2009
Caviphantes Oi, 1960
 225. *C. dobrogicus* (Dumitrescu & Miller, 1962)
Centromerus Dahl, 1886
 226. *C. minor* Tanasevitch, 1990
 227. *C. sylvaticus* (Blackwall, 1841)
Ceratinella Emerton, 1882
 228. *C. brevis* (Wider, 1834)
Collinsia O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1913
 229. *C. inerrans* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1885)
Dactylopiastes Simon, 1884
 230. *D. digiticeps* (Simon, 1881)
Dicymbium Menge, 1868
 231. *D. nigrum* (Blackwall, 1834)
Diplocephalus Bertkau, 1883
 232. *D. picinus* (Blackwall, 1841)
 233. *D. transcaucasicus* Tanasevitch, 1990
Diplostyla Emerton, 1882
 234. *D. concolor* (Wider, 1834)
Entelecara Simon, 1884
 235. *E. acuminata* (Wider, 1834)
 236. *E. erythropus* (Westring, 1851)
Erigone Audouin, 1826
 237. *E. atra* Blackwall, 1833
 238. *E. dentipalpis* (Wider, 1834)
Erigonoplus Simon, 1884
 239. *E. ninae* Tanasevitch & Fet, 1986
 240. *E. sengleti* Tanasevitch, 2008
 241. *E. zagros* Tanasevitch, 2009
Frontinellina van Helsdingen, 1969
 242. *F. frutetorum* (C.L. Koch, 1835)
Gnathonarium Karsch, 1881
 243. *G. dentatum* (Wider, 1834)
Gongylidiellum Simon, 1884
 244. *G. murcidum* Simon, 1884
 245. *G. vivum* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1875)
Lepthyphantes Menge, 1866
 246. *L. iranicus* Saaristo & Tanasevitch, 1996
Linyphia Latreille, 1804
 247. *L. hortensis* Sundevall, 1830
 248. *L. triangularis* (Clerck, 1757)
Maso Simon, 1884
 249. *M. sundevalli* (Westring, 1851)
Megalepthyphantes Wunderlich, 1994
 250. *M. camelus* (Tanasevitch, 1990)
 251. *M. kronebergi* (Tanasevitch, 1989)
 252. *M. kuhitangensis* (Tanasevitch, 1989)
 253. *M. nebulosoides* (Wunderlich, 1977)
 254. *M. nebulosus* (Sundevall, 1830)
 255. *M. pseudocollinus* Saaristo, 1997
Mesasigone Tanasevitch, 1989
 256. *M. mira* Tanasevitch, 1989
Microlinyphia Gerhardt, 1928
 257. *M. pusilla* (Sundevall, 1830)
Microneta Menge, 1869
 258. *M. viaria* (Blackwall, 1841)
Neriene Blackwall, 1833
 259. *N. clathrata* (Sundevall, 1830)
 260. *N. emphana* (Walckenaer, 1841)
 261. *N. peltata* (Wider, 1834)
 262. *N. radiata* (Walckenaer, 1841)
Oedothorax Bertkau, 1883
 263. *O. apicatus* (Blackwall, 1850)
 264. *O. meridionalis* Tanasevitch, 1987
Palliduphantes Saaristo & Tanasevitch, 2001
 265. *P. elburz* Tanasevitch, 2017
 266. *P. khobarum* (Charitonov, 1947)
 267. *P. sbordonii* (Brignoli, 1970)
Pelecopsis Simon, 1864
 268. *P. laptevi* Tanasevitch & Fet, 1986
 269. *P. parallela* (Wider, 1834)
Piniphantes Saaristo & Tanasevitch, 1996

270. *P. pinicola* (Simon, 1884)
Pocadicnemis Simon, 1884
271. *P. pumila* (Blackwall, 1841)
Poeciloneta Kulczyński, 1894
272. *P. variegata* (Blackwall, 1841)
Porrhomma Simon, 1884
273. *P. convexum* (Westring, 1851)
274. *P. microphthalmum* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871)
275. *P. pallidum* Jackson, 1913
Prinerigone Millidge, 1988
276. *P. vagans* (Audouin, 1826)
Scutpelecopsis Marusik & Gnelitsa, 2009
277. *S. procer* Wunderlich, 2011
278. *S. wunderlichi* Marusik & Gnelitsa, 2009
Sengletus Tanasevitch, 2008
279. *S. extricatus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876)
280. *S. latus* Tanasevitch, 2009
Silometopus Simon, 1926
281. *S. reussi* (Thorell, 1871)
Sintula Simon, 1884
282. *S. corniger* (Blackwall, 1856)
Stemonyphantes Menge, 1866
283. *S. agnatus* Tanasevitch, 1990
284. *S. arta* Eshyunin & Zamani, 2021
285. *S. verkana* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
Styloctetor Simon, 1884
286. *S. logunovi* (Eskov & Marusik, 1994)
287. *S. romanus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873)
Tenuiphantes Saaristo & Tanasevitch, 1996
288. *T. perseus* (van Helsdingen, 1977)
289. *T. tenuis* (Blackwall, 1852)
Trematocephalus Dahl, 1886
290. *T. cristatus* (Wider, 1834)
Trichoncoides Denis, 1950
291. *T. piscator* (Simon, 1884)
Troglohyphantes Joseph, 1882
292. *T. paulusi* Thaler, 2002

Walckenaeria Blackwall, 1833
293. *W. acuminata* Blackwall, 1833
294. *W. alticeps* (Denis, 1952)
295. *W. furcillata* (Menge, 1869)
Nesticidae Simon, 1894
Aituaria Eshyunin & Efimik, 1998
296. *A. iranica* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
Theridiosomatidae Simon, 1881
Theridiosoma O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879
297. *T. gemmosum* (L. Koch, 1877)
Araneidae Clerck, 1757
Aculepeira Chamberlin & Ivie, 1942
298. *A. armida* (Audouin, 1826)
299. *A. ceropegia* (Walckenaer, 1802)
300. *A. talishia* (Zawadsky, 1902)
Agalenatea Archer, 1951
301. *A. redii* (Scopoli, 1763)
Araneus Clerck, 1757
302. *A. angulatus* Clerck, 1757
303. *A. circe* (Audouin, 1826)
304. *A. diadematus* Clerck, 1757
305. *A. grossus* (C.L. Koch, 1844)
306. *A. marmoreus* Clerck, 1757
Araniella Chamberlin & Ivie, 1942
307. *A. alpica* (L. Koch, 1869)
308. *A. cucurbitina* (Clerck, 1757)
309. *A. inconspicua* (Simon, 1874)
310. *A. mithra* Zamani, Marusik & Šestáková, 2020
311. *A. opisthographa* (Kulczyński, 1905)
312. *A. villanii* Zamani, Marusik & Šestáková, 2020
Argiope Audouin, 1826
313. *A. ahngeri* Spassky, 1932
314. *A. anasuja* Thorell, 1887
315. *A. bruennichi* (Scopoli, 1772)
316. *A. lobata* (Pallas, 1772)
317. *A. sector* (Forsskål, 1776)
318. *A. trifasciata* (Forsskål, 1775)

***Cercidia* Thorell, 1869**

319. *C. prominens* (Westring, 1851)

***Cyclosa* Menge, 1866**

320. *C. conica* (Pallas, 1772)

321. *C. sierrae* Simon, 1870

***Cyrtophora* Simon, 1864**

322. *C. citricola* (Forsskål, 1775)

***Gibbaranea* Archer, 1951**

323. *G. bituberculata* (Walckenaer, 1802)

324. *G. gibbosa* (Walckenaer, 1802)

325. *G. ullrichi* (Hahn, 1835)

***Hypsosinga* Ausserer, 1871**

326. *H. albovittata* (Westring, 1851)

327. *H. heri* (Hahn, 1831)

328. *H. pygmaea* (Sundevall, 1831)

329. *H. sanguinea* (C.L. Koch, 1844)

***Larinia* Simon, 1874**

330. *L. chloris* (Audouin, 1826)

***Larinioides* Caporiacco, 1934**

331. *L. cornutus* (Clerck, 1757)

332. *L. ixobolus* (Thorell, 1873)

333. *L. suspicax* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876)

***Leviellus* Wunderlich, 2004**

334. *L. caspicus* (Simon, 1889)

***Mangora* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889**

335. *M. acalypha* (Walckenaer, 1802)

***Neoscona* Simon, 1864**

336. *N. adianta* (Walckenaer, 1802)

337. *N. isatis* Zamani, Marusik & Šestáková, 2020

338. *N. spasskyi* (Brignoli, 1983)

339. *N. subfusca* (C.L. Koch, 1837)

340. *N. theisi* (Walckenaer, 1841)

***Nuctenea* Simon, 1864**

341. *N. umbratica* (Clerck, 1757)

***Poltys* C.L. Koch, 1843**

342. *P. nagpurensis* Tikader, 1982

***Singa* C.L. Koch, 1836**

343. *S. hamata* (Clerck, 1757)

344. *S. lucina* (Audouin, 1826)

345. *S. neta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1874)

346. *S. semiatra* L. Koch, 1867

***Siwa* Grasshoff, 1970**

347. *S. atomaria* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876)

***Zilla* C.L. Koch, 1834**

348. *Z. diodia* (Walckenaer, 1802)

***Zygiella* F. O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1902**

349. *Z. x-notata* (Clerck, 1757)

Titanoecidae Lehtinen, 1967

***Nurscia* Simon, 1874**

350. *N. albomaculata* (Lucas, 1846)

351. *N. albosignata* Simon, 1874

***Titanoeca* Thorell, 1870**

352. *T. caucasica* Dunin, 1985

353. *T. schineri* L. Koch, 1872

354. *T. turkmenia* Wunderlich, 1995

355. *T. ukrainica* Guryanova, 1992

Dictynidae O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871

***Ajmonia* Caporiacco, 1934**

356. *A. rajaeii* Zamani & Marusik, 2017

***Archaeodictyna* Caporiacco, 1928**

357. *A. consecuta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

***Argenna* Thorell, 1870**

358. *A. patula* (Simon, 1874)

359. *A. subnigra* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1861)

***Argyroneta* Latreille, 1804**

360. *A. aquatica* (Clerck, 1757)

***Brigittea* Lehtinen, 1967**

361. *B. avicenna* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

362. *B. innocens* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

363. *B. latens* (Fabricius, 1775)

***Brommella* Tullgren, 1948**

364. *B. falcigera* (Balogh, 1935)

***Devade* Simon, 1884**

365. *D. naderii* Zamani & Marusik, 2017

366. *D. tenella* (Tyshchenko 1965)

***Dictyna* Sundevall, 1833**

367. *D. arundinacea* (Linnaeus, 1758)

368. *D. ottoi* Marusik & Koponen, 2017
Kharitonovia Esyunin, Zamani & Tuneva, 2017

369. *K. uzbekistanica* (Charitonov, 1946)
Lathys Simon, 1884

370. *L. humilis* (Blackwall, 1855)

371. *L. lehtineni* Kovblyuk, Kastrygina & Omelko, 2014

372. *L. spasskyi* Andreeva & Tystshenko, 1969

Marilynia Lehtinen, 1967

373. *M. bicolor* (Simon, 1870)

Nigma Lehtinen, 1967

374. *N. flavescens* (Walckenaer, 1830)

375. *N. laeta* (Spassky, 1952)

Paratheuma Bryant, 1940

376. *P. enigmatica* Zamani, Marusik & Berry, 2016

Zodariidae Thorell, 1881

Acanthinozodium Denis, 1966

377. *A. armita* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

378. *A. atrisa* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

379. *A. diara* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

380. *A. dorsa* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

381. *A. elburzicum* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

382. *A. kiana* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

383. *A. masa* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

384. *A. niusha* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

385. *A. parmida* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

386. *A. parysatis* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

387. *A. sorani* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

Lachesana Strand, 1932

388. *L. insensibilis* Jocqué, 1991

389. *L. kavirensis* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

390. *L. perseus* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

Parazodarion Ovtchinnikov, Ahmad & Gurko, 2009

391. *P. raddei* (Simon, 1889)

Pax Levy, 1990

392. *P. ellipita* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

393. *P. leila* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

Trygetus Simon, 1882

394. *T. cyrus* Zamani & Marusik, 2022

395. *T. susianus* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

Zodariellum Andreeva & Tystshenko, 1968

396. *Z. proshynskii* (Nenilin & Fet, 1985)

Zodarion Walckenaer, 1826

397. *Z. buettikeri* (Ono & Jocqué, 1986)

398. *Z. lutipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

399. *Z. talyschicum* Dunin & Nenilin, 1987

Agelenidae C.L. Koch, 1837

Agelena Walckenaer, 1805

400. *A. labyrinthica* (Clerck, 1757)

401. *A. orientalis* C.L. Koch, 1837

Asiascape Zamani & Marusik, 2020

402. *A. parthica* Zamani & Marusik, 2020

Azerithonica Guseinov, Marusik & Koponen, 2005

403. *A. hyrcanica* Guseinov, Marusik & Koponen, 2005

404. *A. sagartia* Zamani & Marusik, 2019

Benoitia Lehtinen, 1967

405. *B. lepida* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876)

Persilena Zamani & Marusik, 2020

406. *P. sengleti* Zamani & Marusik, 2020

Persiscape Zamani & Marusik, 2020

407. *P. caspica* Zamani & Marusik, 2020

408. *P. ecbatana* Zamani & Marusik, 2020

409. *P. gideoni* (Levy, 1996)

410. *P. levyi* (Guseinov, Marusik & Koponen, 2005)

411. *P. nassirkhanii* Zamani & Marusik, 2020

412. *P. zagrosensis* Zamani & Marusik, 2020

Tegenaria Latreille, 1804

413. *T. alamto* Zamani, Marusik & Malek-Hosseini, 2018

414. *T. arsacia* Zamani & Marusik, 2019
415. *T. daylamanica* Zamani & Marusik, 2019
416. *T. domestica* (Clerck, 1757)
417. *T. eros* Zamani & Marusik, 2019
418. *T. guseinovi* Zamani & Marusik, 2019
419. *T. halidi* Guseinov, Marusik & Koponen, 2005
420. *T. lenkoranica* (Guseinov, Marusik & Koponen, 2005)
421. *T. pagana* C.L. Koch, 1840
422. *T. rahnamayi* Zamani & Marusik, 2019
423. *T. shirin* Zamani & Marusik, 2019
424. *T. zamani* Marusik & Omelko, 2014

Amaurobiidae Thorell, 1870

***Amaurobius* C.L. Koch, 1837**

425. *A. erberi* (Keyserling, 1863)

***Eurobius* Zamani & Marusik, 2021**

426. *E. parthicus* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

Zoropsidae Bertkau, 1882

***Zoropsis* Simon, 1878**

427. *Z. lutea* (Thorell, 1875)

Miturgidae Simon, 1886

***Prochora* Simon, 1886**

428. *P. lycosiformis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

***Zora* C.L. Koch, 1847**

429. *Z. huseynovi* Zamani & Marusik, 2017
430. *Z. manicata* Simon, 1878
431. *Z. nemoralis* (Blackwall, 1861)
432. *Z. pardalis* Simon, 1878
433. *Z. silvestris* Kulczyński, 1897
434. *Z. spinimana* (Sundevall, 1833)

Cheiracanthiidae Wagner, 1887

***Cheiracanthium* C.L. Koch, 1839**

435. *C. elegans* Thorell, 1875
436. *C. erraticum* (Walckenaer, 1802)

437. *C. iranicum* Esyunin & Zamani, 2020

438. *C. mildei* L. Koch, 1864

439. *C. montanum* L. Koch, 1877

440. *C. pennyi* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873

441. *C. punctorium* (Villers, 1789)

442. *C. virescens* (Sundevall, 1833)

Cybaeidae Banks, 1892

***Paracedicus* Fet, 1993**

443. *P. darvishi* Mirshamsi, 2018

444. *P. gennadii* (Fet, 1993)

445. *P. kasatkini* Zamani & Marusik, 2017

Hahniidae Bertkau, 1878

***Hahnia* C.L. Koch, 1841**

446. *H. deiocesi* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

447. *H. nava* (Blackwall, 1841)

448. *H. rossii* Brignoli, 1977

***Mastigusa* Menge, 1854**

449. *M. arietina* (Thorell, 1871)

Oxyopidae Thorell, 1869

***Oxyopes* Latreille, 1804**

450. *O. badhyzicus* Mikhailov & Fet, 1986

451. *O. globifer* Simon, 1876

452. *O. heterophthalmus* (Latreille, 1804)

453. *O. iranicus* Esyunin, Rad & Kamoneh, 2011

454. *O. lineatus* Latreille, 1806

455. *O. mediterraneus* Levy, 1999

456. *O. sobrinus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872

***Peucetia* Thorell, 1869**

457. *P. arabica* Simon, 1882

Pisauridae Simon, 1890

***Pisaura* Simon, 1886**

458. *P. mirabilis* (Clerck, 1757)

459. *P. novicia* (L. Koch, 1878)

Lycosidae Sundevall, 1833

Alopecosa Simon, 1885

460. *A. aculeata* (Clerck, 1757)
461. *A. albofasciata* (Brullé, 1832)
462. *A. cursor* (Hahn, 1831)
463. *A. farinosa* (Herman, 1879)
464. *A. murphyorum* Zamani, Nadolny,
Esyunin & Marusik, 2022
465. *A. pekari* Shafaie, Koponen,
Nadolny, Kunt & Mirshamsi, 2022
466. *A. pulverulenta* (Clerck, 1757)
467. *A. robertsi* Zamani, Nadolny,
Esyunin & Marusik, 2022
468. *A. schmidtii* (Hahn, 1835)
469. *A. trabalis* (Clerck, 1757)

Arctosa C.L. Koch, 1847

470. *A. bamiana* (Roewer, 1960)
471. *A. cinerea* (Fabricius, 1777)
472. *A. leopardus* (Sundevall, 1833)
473. *A. maculata* (Hahn, 1822)
474. *A. perita* (Latreille, 1799)
475. *A. similis* Schenkel, 1938
476. *A. stigmosa* (Thorell, 1875)
477. *A. tbilisiensis* Mcheidze, 1946

Aulonia C.L. Koch, 1847

478. *A. kratochvili* Dunin, Buchar &
Absolon, 1986

**Bogdocosa Ponomarev & Belosludtsev
2008**

479. *B. kronebergi* (Andreeva, 1976)

Draposa Kronstedt, 2010

480. *D. oakleyi* (Gravely, 1924)

Evippa Simon, 1882

481. *E. amitaii* Armiach Steinpress,
Alderweireldt, Cohen, Chipman &
Gavish-Regev, 2021
482. *E. eltonica* Dunin, 1994
483. *E. fortis* Roewer, 1955
484. *E. luteipalpis* Roewer, 1955
485. *E. onager* Simon, 1895
486. *E. praelongipes* (O. Pickard-
Cambridge, 1871)

Geolycosa Montgomery, 1904

487. *G. vultuosa* (C.L. Koch, 1838)

Halocosa Azarkina & Trilikauskas, 2019

488. *H. cereipes* (L. Koch, 1878)

Hippasa Simon, 1885

489. *H. deserticola* Simon, 1889

Hogna Simon, 1885

490. *H. effera* (O. Pickard-Cambridge,
1872)

491. *H. radiata* (Latreille, 1817)

Karakumosa Logunov & Ponomarev, 2020

492. *K. golestanica* Shafaie, Nadolny &
Mirshamsi, 2022

493. *K. medica* (Pocock, 1889) (?)

494. *K. sarvari* Shafaie, Nadolny &
Mirshamsi, 2022

495. *K. shmatkoi* Logunov & Ponomarev,
2020

496. *K. turanica* Logunov & Ponomarev,
2020

497. *K. yahaghii* Shafaie, Nadolny &
Mirshamsi, 2022

498. *K. zyuzini* Logunov & Ponomarev,
2020

Lycosa Latreille, 1804

499. *L. aragogi* Nadolny & Zamani, 2017

500. *L. elymaisa* Zamani & Nadolny,
2022

501. *L. macrophthalma* Nadolny &
Zamani, 2020

502. *L. piochardi* Simon, 1876

503. *L. praegrans* C.L. Koch, 1836

504. *L. singoriensis* (Laxmann, 1770)

505. *L. soboutii* Shafaie, Nadolny &
Mirshamsi, 2022

Pardosa C.L. Koch, 1847

506. *P. aenigmatica* Tongiorgi, 1966

507. *P. azerifalcata* Marusik, Guseinov &
Koponen, 2003

508. *P. buchari* Ovtsharenko, 1979

509. *P. colchica* Mcheidze, 1947

510. *P. consimilis* Nosek, 1905

511. *P. dagestana* Buchar & Thaler, 1998

512. *P. donabila* Roewer, 1955

513. *P. hortensis* (Thorell, 1872)

514. *P. incerta* Nosek, 1905
 515. *P. italica* Tongiorgi, 1966
 516. *P. jaikensis* Ponomarev, 2007
 517. *P. luctinosa* Simon, 1876
 518. *P. lugubris* (Walckenaer, 1802)
 519. *P. mirzakhaniae* Shafaie, Mirshamsi, Aliabadian, Moradmand & Marusik, 2018
 520. *P. morosa* (L. Koch, 1870)
 521. *P. nebulosa* (Thorell, 1872)
 522. *P. ovtchinnikovi* Ballarin, Marusik, Omelko & Koponen, 2012
 523. *P. paludicola* (Clerck, 1757)
 524. *P. persiana* Marusik & Nadolny, 2020
 525. *P. persica* (Roewer, 1955)
 526. *P. pontica* (Thorell, 1875)
 527. *P. proxima* (C.L. Koch, 1847)
 528. *P. roscai* (Roewer, 1951)
 529. *P. tatarica* (Thorell, 1875)
 530. *P. zagrosica* Zamani & Nadolny, 2022
 531. *P. zonsteini* Ballarin, Marusik, Omelko & Koponen, 2012
- Pirata Sundevall, 1833**
 532. *P. piraticus* (Clerck, 1757)
- Piratula Roewer, 1960**
 533. *P. latitans* (Blackwall, 1841)
 534. *P. raika* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
- Trochosa C.L. Koch, 1847**
 535. *T. hispanica* Simon, 1870
 536. *T. marusiki* Shafaie, Koponen, Nadolny, Kunt & Mirshamsi, 2022
 537. *T. robusta* (Simon, 1876)
 538. *T. ruricola* (De Geer, 1778)
 539. *T. terricola* Thorell, 1856
 540. *T. urbana* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876
- Wadicosa Zyuzin, 1985**
 541. *W. commoventa* Zyuzin, 1985
 542. *W. fidelis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
- Xerolycosa Dahl, 1908**
543. *X. miniata* (C.L. Koch, 1834)
- Prodidomidae Simon, 1884**
- Prodidomus Hentz, 1847**
 544. *P. inexpectatus* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
 545. *P. redikorzevi* Spassky, 1940
- Zimiris Simon, 1882**
 546. *Z. doriae* Simon, 1882
- Gnaphosidae Banks, 1892**
- Anagraphis Simon, 1893**
 547. *A. pallens* Simon, 1893
- Aphantaulax Simon, 1878**
 548. *A. trifasciata* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
- Berinda Roewer, 1928**
 549. *B. hoerwegi* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
- Berlandina Dalmas, 1922**
 550. *B. afghana* Denis, 1958
 551. *B. artaxerxes* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
 552. *B. caspica* Ponomarev, 1979
 553. *B. cinerea* (Menge, 1872)
 554. *B. mesopotamica* Al-Khazali, 2020
 555. *B. nabozhenkoi* Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006
 556. *B. plumalis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
- Callilepis Westring, 1874**
 557. *C. nocturna* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Callipelis Zamani & Marusik, 2017**
 558. *C. deserticola* Zamani & Marusik, 2017
- Civizelotes Senglet, 2012**
 559. *C. caucasius* (L. Koch, 1866)
 560. *C. solstitialis* (Levy, 1998)
- Cryptodrassus Miller, 1943**
 561. *C. helvolus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 562. *C. iranicus* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
- Drassodes Westring, 1851**

563. *D. chybyndensis* Esyunin & Tuneva, 2002
564. *D. cupreus* (Blackwall, 1834)
565. *D. lapidosus* (Walckenaer, 1802)
566. *D. lutescens* (C.L. Koch, 1839)
567. *D. marusiki* Esyunin & Zamani, 2019
568. *D. persianus* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
569. *D. pubescens* (Thorell, 1856)
570. *D. robatus* Roewer, 1961
571. *D. villosus* (Thorell, 1856)
- Drassyllus Chamberlin, 1922**
572. *D. crimeaensis* Kovblyuk, 2003
573. *D. dadia* Komnenov & Chatzaki, 2016
574. *D. praeficus* (L. Koch, 1866)
575. *D. pusillus* (C.L. Koch, 1833)
576. *D. sur* Tuneva & Esyunin, 2003
577. *D. villicoides* (Giltay, 1932)
- Echemus Simon, 1878**
578. *E. caspicus* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
- Fedotovia Charitonov, 1946**
579. *F. uzbekistanica* Charitonov, 1946
- Gnaphosa Latreille, 1804**
580. *G. bithynica* Kulczyński, 1903
581. *G. dolosa* Herman, 1879
582. *G. leporina* (L. Koch, 1866)
583. *G. lucifuga* (Walckenaer, 1802)
584. *G. petrobia* L. Koch, 1872
585. *G. qamsarica* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
586. *G. saurica* Ovtsharenko, Platnick & Song, 1992
587. *G. steppica* Ovtsharenko, Platnick & Song, 1992
588. *G. tigrina* Simon, 1878
589. *G. ukrainica* Ovtsharenko, Platnick & Song, 1992
- Haplodrassus Chamberlin, 1922**
590. *H. caspius* Ponomarev & Belosludtsev, 2008
591. *H. dalmatensis* (L. Koch, 1866)
592. *H. medes* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
593. *H. ovtchinnikovi* Ponomarev, 2008
594. *H. pseudosignifer* Marusik, Hippa & Koponen, 1996
595. *H. pugnans* (Simon, 1880)
596. *H. qashqai* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
597. *H. rhodanicus* (Simon, 1914)
598. *H. signifer* (C.L. Koch, 1839)
599. *H. silvestris* (Blackwall, 1833)
- Iranotricha Zamani & Marusik, 2018**
600. *I. lutensis* Zamani & Marusik, 2018
- Leptopilos Levy, 2009**
601. *L. levantinus* Levy, 2009
- Marinarozelotes Ponomarev, 2020**
602. *M. achaemenes* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
603. *M. adriaticus* (Caporiacco, 1951)
604. *M. fuscipes* (L. Koch, 1866)
605. *M. jaxartensis* (Kroneberg, 1875)
606. *M. lyonneti* (Audouin, 1826)
607. *M. malkini* (Platnick & Murphy, 1984)
608. *M. manytchensis* (Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006)
609. *M. miniglossus* (Levy, 2009)
- Marjanus Chatzaki, 2018**
610. *M. isfahanicus* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
- Megamyрмаekion Reuss, 1834**
611. *M. caudatum* Reuss, 1834
- Micaria Westring, 1851**
612. *M. albovittata* (Lucas, 1846)
613. *M. atropatene* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
614. *M. coarctata* (Lucas, 1846)
615. *M. dives* (Lucas, 1846)
616. *M. formicaria* (Sundevall, 1831)
617. *M. fulgens* (Walckenaer, 1802)
618. *M. ignea* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872

619. *M. kopetdaghensis* Mikhailov, 1986
 620. *M. lenzi* Bösenberg, 1899
 621. *M. pallipes* (Lucas, 1846)
 622. *M. pulicaria* (Sundevall, 1831)
 623. *M. rossica* Thorell, 1875
 624. *M. subopaca* Westring, 1861
- Minosia Dalmas, 1921**
 625. *M. simeonica* Levy, 1995
- Minosiella Dalmas, 1921**
 626. *M. intermedia* Denis, 1958
- Nomisia Dalmas, 1921**
 627. *N. ameretatae* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
 628. *N. aussereri* (L. Koch, 1872)
 629. *N. conigera* (Spassky, 1941)
 630. *N. exornata* (C.L. Koch, 1839)
 631. *N. negebensis* Levy, 1995
 632. *N. palaestina* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 633. *N. ripariensis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
- Parasyrisca Schenkel, 1963**
 634. *P. turkenica* Ovtsharenko, Platnick & Marusik, 1995
- Phaeoecetus Simon, 1893**
 635. *P. braccatus* (L. Koch, 1866)
- Poecilochroa Westring, 1874**
 636. *P. senilis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
- Pterotricha Kulczyński, 1903**
 637. *P. dalmasi* Fage, 1929
 638. *P. kovblyuki* Zamani & Marusik, 2018
 639. *P. montana* Zamani & Marusik, 2018
 640. *P. pseudoparasasyriaca* Nuruyeva & Huseynov, 2016
 641. *P. strandi* Spassky, 1936
- Scotophaeus Simon, 1893**
 642. *S. anahita* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
 643. *S. blackwalli* (Thorell, 1871)
644. *S. elburzensis* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
 645. *S. scutulatus* (L. Koch, 1866)
- Setaphis Simon, 1893**
 646. *S. carmeli* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
- Shaitan Kovblyuk, Kastrygina & Marusik, 2013**
 647. *S. angramainyu* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
- Sidydrassus Esyunin & Tuneva, 2002**
 648. *S. shumakovi* (Spassky, 1934)
- Sosticus Chamberlin, 1922**
 649. *S. loricatus* (L. Koch, 1866)
 650. *S. montanus* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
- Synaphosus Platnick & Shadab, 1980**
 651. *S. martinezi* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
 652. *S. neali* Ovtsharenko, Levy & Platnick, 1994
 653. *S. palearcticus* Ovtsharenko, Levy & Platnick, 1994
 654. *S. shirin* Ovtsharenko, Levy & Platnick, 1994
- Talanites Simon, 1893**
 655. *T. dunini* Platnick & Ovtsharenko, 1991
 656. *T. fagei* Spassky, 1938
- Trachyzelotes Lohmander, 1944**
 657. *T. pedestris* (C.L. Koch, 1837)
- Turkozelotes Kovblyuk & Seyyar, 2009**
 658. *T. kazachstanicus* (Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006)
 659. *T. mccowani* (Chatzaki & Russell-Smith, 2017)
- Zagrotus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021**
 660. *Z. apophysalis* Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
 661. *Z. bifurcatus* (Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021)
 662. *Z. borna* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

663. *Z. parla* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
Zelotes Gistel, 1848

664. *Z. alpujarraensis* Senglet, 2011
665. *Z. apricorum* (L. Koch, 1876)
666. *Z. babunaensis* (Drensky, 1929)
667. *Z. chaniaensis* Senglet, 2011
668. *Z. electus* (C.L. Koch, 1839)
669. *Z. fulvaster* (Simon, 1878)
670. *Z. harmeron* Levy, 2009
671. *Z. hyrcanus* Zamani, Chatzaki,
Esyunin & Marusik, 2021
672. *Z. khostensis* Kovblyuk &
Ponomarev, 2008
673. *Z. laetus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge,
1872)
674. *Z. longipes* (L. Koch, 1866)
675. *Z. metellus* Roewer, 1928
676. *Z. mundus* (Kulczyński, 1897)
677. *Z. potanini* Schenkel, 1963
678. *Z. puritanus* Chamberlin, 1922
679. *Z. scrutatus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge,
1872)
680. *Z. zekharya* Levy, 2009

Cithaeronidae Simon, 1893

Cithaeron O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872

681. *C. praedonius* O. Pickard-
Cambridge, 1872

Anyphaenidae Bertkau, 1878

Anyphaena Sundevall, 1833

682. *A. accentuata* (Walckenaer, 1802)

Liocranidae Simon, 1897

Agroeca Westring, 1861

683. *A. angirasu* Zamani & Marusik,
2021
684. *A. cuprea* Menge, 1873
685. *A. inopina* O. Pickard-Cambridge,
1886
686. *A. lusatica* (L. Koch, 1875)
687. *A. parva* Bosmans, 2011

Mesiotelus Simon, 1897

688. *M. caucasicus* Zamani & Marusik,
2021

689. *M. kulczynskii* Charitonov, 1946
690. *M. patricki* Zamani & Marusik, 2021
691. *M. scopensis* Drensky, 1935

Sestakovaia Zamani & Marusik, 2021

692. *S. hyrcania* Zamani & Marusik,
2021

Clubionidae Wagner, 1887

Clubiona Latreille, 1804

693. *C. golovatchi* Mikhailov, 1990
694. *C. hyrcanica* Mikhailov, 1990
695. *C. juvenis* Simon, 1878
696. *C. lutescens* Westring, 1851
697. *C. mazandarana* Mikhailov, 2003
698. *C. neglecta* O. Pickard-Cambridge,
1862
699. *C. phragmitis* C.L. Koch, 1843
700. *C. pseudoneglecta* Wunderlich,
1994

Porrhoclubiona Lohmander, 1944

701. *P. genevensis* (L. Koch, 1866)
702. *P. moradmandi* Marusik & Omelko,
2018
703. *P. vegeta* (Simon, 1918)

Corinnidae Karsch, 1880

Castianeira Keyserling, 1879

704. *C. arnoldii* Charitonov, 1946

Phrurolithidae Banks, 1892

Bosselaerius Zamani & Marusik, 2020

705. *B. hyrcanicus* Zamani & Marusik,
2020

Phrurolithus C.L. Koch, 1839

706. *P. azarkinae* Zamani & Marusik,
2020
707. *P. festivus* (C.L. Koch, 1835)
708. *P. pullatus* Kulczyński, 1897

Trachelidae Simon, 1897

Orthobula Simon, 1897

709. *O. charitonovi* (Mikhailov, 1986)
710. *O. mikhailovi* Marusik, 2021

Trachelas L. Koch, 1872

711. *T. minor* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872

Selenopidae Simon, 1897

Selenops Latreille, 1819

712. *S. radiatus* Latreille, 1819

Sparassidae Bertkau, 1872

Cebrennus Simon, 1880

713. *C. rambodjavani* Moradmand, Zamani & Jäger, 2016

Eusparassus Simon, 1903

714. *E. doriae* (Simon, 1874)

715. *E. kronebergi* Denis, 1958

716. *E. mesopotamicus* Moradmand & Jäger, 2012

717. *E. oculatus* (Kroneberg, 1875)

718. *E. xerxes* (Pocock, 1901)

Micrommata Latreille, 1804

719. *M. virescens* (Clerck, 1757)

Olios Walckenaer, 1837

720. *O. sericeus* (Kroneberg, 1875)

721. *O. stimulator* (Simon, 1897) (?)

Pseudomicrommata Järvi, 1912

722. *P. mokranica* Moradmand, Zamani & Jäger, 2019

Spariolenus Simon, 1880

723. *S. aratta* Moradmand & Jäger, 2011

724. *S. fathpouri* Moradmand, 2017

725. *S. hormozii* Moradmand, 2017

726. *S. iranomaximus* Moradmand & Jäger, 2011

727. *S. khozestanus* Zamani, 2016

728. *S. manesht* Moradmand & Jäger, 2011

729. *S. mansourii* Moradmand, 2017

730. *S. zagros* Moradmand & Jäger, 2011

Philodromidae Thorell, 1870

Philodromus Walckenaer, 1826

731. *P. aureolus* (Clerck, 1757)

732. *P. buxi* Simon, 1884

733. *P. cespitem* (Walckenaer, 1802)

734. *P. dispar* Walckenaer, 1826

735. *P. emarginatus* (Schrank, 1803)

736. *P. longipalpis* Simon, 1870

737. *P. margaritatus* (Clerck, 1757)

738. *P. praedatus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871

739. *P. rufus* (Walckenaer, 1826)

Pulchellodromus Wunderlich, 2012

740. *P. medius* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

Rhysodromus Schick, 1965

741. *R. fallax* (Sundevall, 1833)

742. *R. genoensis* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

743. *R. hierosolymitanus* (Levy, 1977)

744. *R. medes* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

Thanatus C.L. Koch, 1837

745. *T. arenarius* L. Koch, 1872

746. *T. atratus* Simon, 1875

747. *T. fabricii* (Audouin, 1826)

748. *T. formicinus* (Clerck, 1757)

749. *T. fornicatus* Simon, 1897

750. *T. imbecillus* L. Koch, 1878

751. *T. kitabensis* Charitonov, 1946

752. *T. lesserti* (Roewer, 1951)

753. *T. oblongiusculus* (Lucas, 1846)

754. *T. pictus* L. Koch, 1881

755. *T. saraevi* Ponomarev, 2007

756. *T. setiger* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

757. *T. vulgaris* Simon, 1870

Tibellus Simon, 1875

758. *T. oblongus* (Walckenaer, 1802)

Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833

Bassaniodes Pocock, 1903

759. *B. cribratus* (Simon, 1885)

760. *B. loeffleri* (Roewer, 1955)

761. *B. rectilineus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

762. *B. tristrami* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

Diaea Thorell, 1869

763. *D. dorsata* (Fabricius, 1777)

764. *D. livens* Simon, 1876
 765. *D. osmanii* Zamani & Marusik, 2017
Ebrechtella Dahl, 1907
 766. *E. tricuspidata* (Fabricius, 1775)
Firmicus Simon, 1895
 767. *F. dewitzi* Simon, 1899
Heriaeus Simon, 1875
 768. *H. buffoni* (Audouin, 1826)
 769. *H. graminicola* (Doleschall, 1852)
 770. *H. spinipalpus* Loerbroks, 1983
Misumena Latreille, 1804
 771. *M. vatia* (Clerck, 1757)
Monaeses Thorell, 1869
 772. *M. israeliensis* Levy, 1973
Ozyptila Simon, 1864
 773. *O. aculipalpa* Wunderlich, 1995
 774. *O. atomaria* (Panzer, 1801)
 775. *O. claveata* (Walckenaer, 1837)
 776. *O. grisea* Roewer, 1955
 777. *O. lugubris* (Kroneberg, 1875)
 778. *O. lutosa* Ono & Martens, 2005
 779. *O. makidica* Ono & Martens, 2005
 780. *O. patellibidens* Levy, 1999
 781. *O. praticola* (C.L. Koch, 1837)
 782. *O. simplex* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1862)
 783. *O. tricoloripes* Strand, 1913
Pistius Simon, 1875
 784. *P. truncatus* (Pallas, 1772)
Psammitis Menge, 1876
 785. *P. abramovi* (Marusik & Logunov, 1995)
 786. *P. minor* (Charitonov, 1946)
 787. *P. ninnii fusciventris* (Crome, 1965)
Runcinia Simon, 1875
 788. *R. grammica* (C.L. Koch, 1837)
 789. *R. tarabayevi* Marusik & Logunov, 1990
Spiracme Menge, 1876
 790. *S. striatipes* (L. Koch, 1870)
Stiphropus Gerstaecker, 1873
 791. *S. strandi* Spassky, 1938
Synema Simon, 1864
 792. *S. anatolicum* Demir, Aktaş & Topçu, 2009
 793. *S. globosum* (Fabricius, 1775)
 794. *S. plorator* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
Thomisus Walckenaer, 1805
 795. *T. albohirtus* Simon, 1884
 796. *T. citrinellus* Simon, 1875
 797. *T. onustus* Walckenaer, 1805
 798. *T. unidentatus* Dippenaar-Schoeman & van Harten, 2007
 799. *T. zyuzini* Marusik & Logunov, 1990
Tmarus Simon, 1875
 800. *T. piochardi* (Simon, 1866)
 801. *T. punctatissimus* (Simon, 1870)
 802. *T. stellio* Simon, 1875
Xysticus C.L. Koch, 1835
 803. *X. acerbus* Thorell, 1872
 804. *X. atevs* Ovtsharenko, 1979
 805. *X. audax* (Schrank, 1803)
 806. *X. cor* Canestrini, 1873
 807. *X. cristatus* (Clerck, 1757)
 808. *X. edax* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 809. *X. gallicus* Simon, 1875
 810. *X. kaznakovi* Utochkin, 1968
 811. *X. kempeleni* Thorell, 1872
 812. *X. kochi* Thorell, 1872
 813. *X. kulczynskii* Werjbitzky, 1902
 814. *X. laetus* Thorell, 1875
 815. *X. logunovororum* Blick & Ono, 2021
 816. *X. luctuosus* (Blackwall, 1836)
 817. *X. marusiki* Ono & Martens, 2005
 818. *X. pieperi* Ono & Martens, 2005
 819. *X. turkmenicus* Marusik & Logunov, 1995
 820. *X. xerodermus* Strand, 1913
Salticidae Blackwall, 1841
Aelurillus Simon, 1885
 821. *A. concolor* Kulczyński, 1901
 822. *A. khorasanicus* Azarkina & Mirshamsi, 2014
 823. *A. marusiki* Azarkina, 2002

824. *A. m-nigrum* Kulczyński, 1891
 825. *A. unitibialis* Azarkina, 2002
 826. *A. westi* Azarkina & Zamani, 2019
***Afraflacilla* Berland & Millot, 1941**
 827. *A. arabica* Wesołowska & van Harten, 1994
***Attulus* Simon, 1889**
 828. *A. avocator* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1885)
 829. *A. karakumensis* (Logunov, 1992)
 830. *A. relictarius* (Logunov, 1998)
 831. *A. vilis* (Kulczyński, 1895)
***Ballus* C.L. Koch, 1850**
 832. *B. chalybeius* (Walckenaer, 1802)
***Bianor* Peckham & Peckham, 1886**
 833. *B. albobimaculatus* (Lucas, 1846)
***Carrhotus* Thorell, 1891**
 834. *C. viduus* (C.L. Koch, 1846)
***Chalcoscirtus* Bertkau, 1880**
 835. *C. hosseinieorum* Logunov, Marusik & Mozaffarian, 2002
 836. *C. infimus* (Simon, 1868)
 837. *C. iranicus* Logunov & Marusik, 1999
 838. *C. karakurt* Marusik, 1991
 839. *C. lepidus* Wesołowska, 1996
 840. *C. nigritus* (Thorell, 1875)
 841. *C. parvulus* Marusik, 1991
 842. *C. platnicki* Marusik, 1995
 843. *C. tanasevichi* Marusik, 1991
***Chinattus* Logunov, 1999**
 844. *C. caucasicus* Logunov, 1999
***Cyrba* Simon, 1876**
 845. *C. algerina* (Lucas, 1846)
 846. *C. ocellata* (Kroneberg, 1875)
***Euophrys* C.L. Koch, 1834**
 847. *E. frontalis* (Walckenaer, 1802)
 848. *E. sulphurea* (L. Koch, 1867)
***Evarcha* Simon, 1902**
 849. *E. arcuata* (Clerck, 1757)
 850. *E. dena* Zamani, 2017
 851. *E. insularis* (Metzner, 1999)
 852. *E. negevensis* Prószyński, 2000
 853. *E. praeclara* Prószyński & Wesołowska, 2003
***Heliophanillus* Prószyński, 1989**
 854. *H. fulgens* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
***Heliophanus* C.L. Koch, 1833**
 855. *H. chovdensis* Prószyński, 1982
 856. *H. cupreus* (Walckenaer, 1802)
 857. *H. curvidens* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 858. *H. decoratus* L. Koch, 1875
 859. *H. dunini* Rakov & Logunov, 1997
 860. *H. edentulus* Simon, 1871
 861. *H. equester* L. Koch, 1867
 862. *H. flavipes* (Hahn, 1832)
 863. *H. forcipifer* Kulczyński, 1895
 864. *H. glaucus* Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895
 865. *H. iranus* Wesołowska, 1986
 866. *H. mordax* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 867. *H. verus* Wesołowska, 1986
 868. *H. xerxesi* Logunov, 2009
***Iranattus* Prószyński, 1992**
 869. *I. rectangularis* Prószyński, 1992
***Langona* Simon, 1901**
 870. *L. aperta* (Denis, 1958)
 871. *L. pallidula* Logunov & Rakov, 1998
 872. *L. redii* (Audouin, 1826)
 873. *L. tartarica* (Charitonov, 1946)
***Macaroeris* Wunderlich, 1992**
 874. *M. nidicolens* (Walckenaer, 1802)
***Marpissa* C.L. Koch, 1846**
 875. *M. nivoyi* (Lucas, 1846)
***Mendoza* Peckham & Peckham, 1894**
 876. *M. canestrinii* (Ninni, 1868)
***Menemerus* Simon, 1868**
 877. *M. errabundus* Logunov, 2010
 878. *M. marginatus* (Kroneberg, 1875)
 879. *M. semilimbatus* (Hahn, 1829)
***Mexcala* Peckham & Peckham, 1902**
 880. *M. farsensis* Logunov, 2001
***Mogrus* Simon, 1882**
 881. *M. antoninus* Andreeva, 1976

882. *M. larisae* Logunov, 1995
 883. *M. neglectus* (Simon, 1868)
- Myrmarachne MacLeay, 1839**
 884. *M. formicaria* (De Geer, 1778)
 885. *M. tristis* (Simon, 1882)
- Neon Simon, 1876**
 886. *N. levis* (Simon, 1871)
 887. *N. rayi* (Simon, 1875)
 888. *N. reticulatus* (Blackwall, 1853)
- Pellenes Simon, 1876**
 889. *P. bonus* Logunov, Marusik & Rakov, 1999
 890. *P. brevis* (Simon, 1868)
 891. *P. diagonalis* (Simon, 1868)
 892. *P. epularis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 893. *P. geniculatus* (Simon, 1868)
 894. *P. seriatus* (Thorell, 1875)
- Philaeus Thorell, 1869**
 895. *P. chrysops* (Poda, 1761)
- Phintella Strand, 1906**
 896. *P. castrisiana* (Grube, 1861)
- Phlegra Simon, 1876**
 897. *P. bresnieri* (Lucas, 1846)
 898. *P. cinereofasciata* (Simon, 1868)
 899. *P. dunini* Azarkina, 2004
 900. *P. fasciata* (Hahn, 1826)
 901. *P. tetralineata* (Caporiacco, 1939)
 902. *P. yaelae* Prószyński, 1998
- Plexippoides Prószyński, 1984**
 903. *P. flavescens* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 904. *P. gestroi* (Dalmas, 1920)
 905. *P. insperatus* Logunov, 2021
- Plexippus C.L. Koch, 1846**
 906. *P. clemens* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)
 907. *P. gershomi* Prószyński, 2017
 908. *P. iranus* Logunov, 2009
 909. *P. minor* Wesolowska & van Harten, 2010
 910. *P. paykulli* (Audouin, 1826)
911. *P. strandi* Spassky, 1939
- Proszynskiana Logunov, 1996**
 912. *P. iranica* Logunov, 1996 (?)
 913. *P. izadii* Azarkina & Zamani, 2019
 914. *P. logunovi* Azarkina & Zamani, 2019
- Pseudeuophrys Dahl, 1912**
 915. *P. erratica* (Walckenaer, 1826)
 916. *P. lanigera* (Simon, 1871)
 917. *P. obsoleta* (Simon, 1868)
- Pseudicius Simon, 1885**
 918. *P. badius* (Simon, 1868)
 919. *P. palaestinensis* Strand, 1915
- Rafalus Prószyński, 1999**
 920. *R. variegatus* (Kroneberg, 1875)
- Rudakius Prószyński, 2016**
 921. *R. afghanicus* (Andreeva, Hęciak & Prószyński, 1984)
 922. *R. cinctus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1885)
 923. *R. ludhianaensis* (Tikader, 1974)
 924. *R. rudakii* (Prószyński, 1992)
 925. *R. spasskyi* (Andreeva, Hęciak & Prószyński, 1984)
- Salticus Latreille, 1804**
 926. *S. insperatus* Logunov, 2009
 927. *S. lucasi* Zamani, Hosseini & Moradmam, 2020
 928. *S. noordami* Metzner, 1999
 929. *S. scenicus* (Clerck, 1757)
 930. *S. tricinctus* (C.L. Koch, 1846)
 931. *S. zebraneus* (C.L. Koch, 1837)
- Stenaelurillus Simon, 1886**
 932. *S. marusiki* Logunov, 2001
- Synageles Simon, 1876**
 933. *S. persianus* Logunov, 2004
- Talavera Peckham & Peckham, 1909**
 934. *T. aequipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871)
- Thyene Simon, 1885**
 935. *T. imperialis* (Rossi, 1846)